

Heats of Solution and Neutralization of Protonic Acids in Acetic Anhydride

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Heats of solution of fluorosulphuric, pyrosulphuric and sulphuric acids in acetic anhydride have been determined and their relative strengths compared. Studies on the heats of neutralization of these protonic acids with bases like pyridine, piperidine α -picoline and potassium acetate have also been carried out with a view to comparing the relative strength of the bases and to explain the nature of the solvent.

THE following mode of ionization of acetic anhydride has been proposed on the basis of solvate formation¹, solvolytic reactions¹⁻³, conductometric^{4,5} and potentiometric⁶ studies :

However, infrared spectral studies⁷ and heats of solution of Lewis acids⁸ have led to the following alternative ionization :

In the present study, heats of solution of fluorosulphuric, pyrosulphuric and sulphuric acids, and their neutralization with α -picoline, pyridine, piperidine and potassium acetate in acetic anhydride have been measured with a view to arrive at some definite conclusion about the ionization of the solvent.

Experimental

The solvent¹, bases¹ and acids⁵ were purified as described earlier. Thermochemical measurements were carried out in an isothermal phase-change calorimeter designed after Dainton and coworkers⁹. The working of the calorimeter and the method of determination of heats of solution and neutralization have been the same as reported earlier¹⁰.

Results and Discussion

Heats of solution: Heat of solution of fluorosulphuric, pyrosulphuric and sulphuric acids in acetic

anhydride in the concentration range studied is 23.71–24.91, 42.12–49.78 and 17.20–18.87 kcal mole⁻¹ respectively (Table 1). The net enthalpy change includes

TABLE 1—HEATS OF SOLUTION OF PROTONIC ACIDS IN ANHYDROUS ACETIC ANHYDRIDE (25 ml)

Acid	Amount of acid g mole	Heat of solution k cal mole ⁻¹
HSO ₃ F	0.000792	24.82
	0.000708	23.71
	0.000470	24.91
H ₂ S ₂ O ₇	0.000404	24.16
	0.000674	42.12
	0.000484	43.45
H ₂ SO ₄	0.000146	49.78
	0.00959	18.47
	0.000615	18.87
	0.000287	17.20

the heat of solvate formation, its ionization and subsequent solvation of the ions formed. Fluorosulphuric acid which is a very strong monobasic acid, dissolves in various solvents producing nearly the same amount of heat¹¹ indicating that the autoprotolysis of the acid is almost complete and as expected the proton gets readily solvated by the solvents. Since heat of dissolution of fluorosulphuric and sulphuric acids in acetic anhydride is independent of acid concentration, the autoprotolysis of these acids is complete. However, there is a marked concentration effect in case of pyrosulphuric acid indicating that the acid is more ionized in dilute solutions than in concentrated solutions. Considering that sulphuric acid normally

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behaves as a dibasic acid, the heat effect seems to be low. There is a possibility that it may behave as a monobasic acid in acetic anhydride as is the case in dimethylformamide¹⁰. The heat changes may be attributed to the following reactions :

Where H_2A and HA are dibasic and monobasic acids respectively. On the basis of heat evolved per mole of the acid, these protonic acids may be assigned the following order of relative acid strength:

But taking into consideration the dibasic nature of pyrosulphuric acid, the order may be reconstituted as

Heats of neutralization: Heats of neutralization of these protonic acids with certain bases are determined to ascertain the probable ionization of the solvent (Table 2). Ionization (ii) seems to be more

TABLE 2—HEATS OF NEUTRALIZATION OF PROTONIC ACIDS WITH BASES IN ANHYDROUS ACETIC ANHYDRIDE (25 ml)

Base	Heat of neutralization*		
	HSO_3F	$\text{H}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_7$	H_2SO_4
Piperidine	8.99	9.66	9.45
Potassium acetate	11.38	11.53	12.70
α -Picoline	15.34	15.28	16.28
Pyridine	15.30	15.23	16.52

* The values given are the mean values for 4-5 experiments.

probable as the heats evolved on neutralization in acetic anhydride are comparable with those in protonic

solvents. The values for heat of neutralization in acetyl chloride where acetylium ions are formed, has been reported to be 41–127 kcal mole⁻¹ by Paul and coworkers¹². Heat of neutralization of α -picoline or pyridine with these protonic acids in acetic anhydride is higher than that of potassium acetate suggesting that acetate ion may not be the anion characteristic of the solvent.

Fluorosulphuric acid reacts with α -picoline, pyridine, potassium acetate and piperidine in acetic anhydride resulting in the evolution of 15.34, 15.30, 11.38 and 8.99 kcal mole⁻¹ of the base neutralized respectively. The reaction may be represented as

Heat of neutralization of piperidine, potassium acetate, α -picoline and pyridine is 9.66, 11.53, 15.28 and 15.23 kcal mole⁻¹ of the base neutralized with pyrosulphuric acid, and 9.45, 12.70, 16.28 and 16.52 kcal mole⁻¹ with sulphuric acid respectively. Since these acids are taken in excess in all the neutralization reactions, it is likely that they may behave as monobasic acids and the neutralization enthalpy may be ascribed to the following reaction:

It is observed that the heat of neutralization values are independent of the concentration of the base. On the basis of these enthalpy values, the bases may be arranged in the following order of strength :

The neutralization products are completely soluble in the solvent. Heat of neutralization in the case of protonic acids compares well with that of Lewis acids⁸ indicating that the nature of the neutralization reactions is the same in both the cases. The major enthalpy change is thus mainly due to the combination of

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \quad \text{OH} \\ \parallel \quad \parallel \\ (\text{CH}_3\text{COCCH}_3)^+ \text{ and } (\text{CH}_3\text{COOCOCH}_2)^- \end{array}$$

ions although other factors like the dissociation of the salt or its precipitation also affect the neutralization enthalpy. Heat of ionization of the unionized solvates of the acid and base may also be absorbed as the reaction proceeds to completion.

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